
**READING STRATEGIES, READING INTERESTS, AND ACADEMIC WRITING
PROFICIENCY OF SENIOR HIGH SCHOOL STUDENTS: A BASIS IN DESIGNING
DISCOURSE-BASED TASKS**

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Abstract

This study investigated the relationship among the reading strategies, reading interests, and academic writing proficiency of the Grade 11 students of Echague National High School. The researchers adopted the Survey of Reading Strategies of Kouider Mohktari and Ravi Sheorey (2002) to identify the reading strategies of the respondents, and a questionnaire from Noortyani (2018) to determine their reading interests. Data were obtained on their writing proficiency by administering the Writing Proficiency Test which is evaluated by inter-raters using Analytical Rubric.

The findings showed that students predominantly used problem-solving strategies while reading and had moderate reading interests, with a positive attitude toward reading. However, their academic writing proficiency was mostly at the developing level. No significant relationship was found between reading interests and writing proficiency, except for two specific reading interests. Additionally, no significant correlation existed between reading strategies and writing proficiency. Finally, there is a significant relationship found between the reading interests and reading strategies of the respondents.

The findings led the researchers to the development of a material titled "Mastering Organization and Global Reading Skills: A Comprehensive Guide for Academic Success", to enhance students' organizational skills in writing and use of global reading strategies.

INTRODUCTION

Reading is an extremely intricate activity in which the reader must actively engage. It requires a lot of intricate abilities that must come together for the reader to succeed. Leipzig (2001) asserts that reading is a complex process that includes motivation, word recognition, comprehension, and fluency. The cognitive processes involved in reading are all focused on the brain, including the mental processes involved in paying attention to details or ignoring a crucial phone call.

Reading strategies are deliberate ways to understand the author's point of view. They are thought to persuade readers to modify their reading habits in order to address task demands, text complexity, and other contextual factors (Olshavsky, 1977). Three categories can be used to group reading strategies, according to Mokhtari & Sheorey (2002): global reading strategies (GLOB), problem-solving strategies (PROB), and support strategies (SUP). The deliberate and well-thought-out methods that readers use to keep an eye on and regulate their reading such as setting goals and skimming the text's length and structure are referred to as global reading strategies. Conversely, readers who employ problem-solving strategies, such as varying their reading speed or making educated guesses about the meaning of words they are unfamiliar with, are able to digest and understand challenging texts more effectively. Finally, support reading strategies are tools or techniques that readers use to help them understand the text.

In connection with the reading strategies, reading interests in this study are included as they reflect students' behavior towards learning and performance. Therefore, students' quality of performance will depend on their interest in doing certain learning activities as it greatly affects whether they are going to perform well or not. Moreover, it plays an essential and necessary role in learning (Ainley et al., 2002). Similarly, interest was described as a favorable attitude toward the subjects, activities, or issues by Pintrich (1989) and Schiefel (1991). Additionally, McWhaw & Abrami (2001) and Alexander & Wade (2000) noted that students' interests will have a significant impact on their learning activities and processes. As a result, this aspect is related to strategies as it affects how students perform in reading.

In connection with the variables discussed above, academic writing proficiency is an interesting variable to investigate alongside reading strategies and reading interests (Amril Amir et al., 2023). Evident of this is the study entitled 'Influence of Reading Strategies and Interests on Exposition Writing Skills in Higher Education Students' conducted by Amril Amir (2023) as it found that students who had a high interest in reading demonstrated better exposition writing skills than those who had a low interest. As Krashen (2016) pointed out, reading is a better way to learn how to write than writing. Thus, there is a significant longitudinal and contemporaneous relationship between reading and writing. As a result, the researchers are curious to know how proficient the respondents are in academic writing and how it relates to their reading interests and strategies.

Therefore, in line with the discussion above, reading strategies, reading interests, and academic writing proficiency are interconnected and each of them plays a significant role in each other. For that reason, the researchers are determined to investigate the relationship between reading strategies and reading interests and the academic writing proficiency of the respondents, as it is mentioned above that writing is learned and enhanced through reading (Cottrell, 2017). Though it was mentioned that reading and writing are significantly connected (Krashen, 2016), there is no specific study that explores the relationship between the reading strategies, reading interests, and academic writing skills of the students. In the study by Merjen et al. (2019), entitled 'Impact of Reading on Students' Writing Ability', they mentioned that not many studies have been done on the effect of reading habits on the problem of academic writing. Therefore, this study will generally focus on a thorough investigation of the relationship between the variables presented in this study and how these relationships can be used as the basis for designing discourse-based tasks that can be used in future endeavors in the education system.

The result of this research will provide an elaborated interpretation of the relationship among the reading strategies, reading interests, and academic writing skills of the

respondents, which will allow them to know the importance of reading strategies and interests in improving academic writing proficiency. As a result, this study could motivate them to involve themselves more often in reading by following the strategies that help them best acquire information from the text. Besides that, this study could help educators enhance the teaching and learning environment by adopting or using the discourse-based tasks that will be developed in this study that are sufficient to meet the needs of diverse learners.

METHODS

Research Design

This study employed a descriptive-correlational design to investigate significant relationships between variables. This design was used to explore the relationship between students' reading strategies, reading interest, and academic writing achievement at Echague National High School. According to Leedy & Ormrod and Williams (Apuke, 2017), data collection in quantitative research measures and assesses knowledge, validating it by testing hypotheses against expert opinions. Additionally, a developmental research methodology was used to provide an empirical framework for creating discourse-based tasks. Ibrahim (2016) states that developmental research offers a basis for developing educational tools and models. The study employed developmental research, specifically focusing on the analysis and development phase of the ADDIE model.

Respondents and Locale of the Study

This study was conducted at Echague National High School, focusing on Grade 11 students enrolled in the Accountancy, Business, and Management (ABM), Humanities and Social Sciences (HUMSS), Technological Vocational Livelihood (TVL), and Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics (STEM) strands. The research sample consists of 192 senior high school students.

Research Instrument

In this research, the researchers adopted the Survey of Reading Strategies of Kouider Mokhtari and Ravi Sheory (2002) to gather the data about the reading strategies. To collect and analyze the data on reading interest, a questionnaire from Noortyani (2018) was adopted, and to obtain data on their writing proficiency, the researchers administered the Analytical Rubric for Writing Proficiency Test.

Data Gathering Procedure and Analysis

Following the revision of the research instruments, the researchers sought formal approval from the principal of Echague National High School to conduct data collection within the Senior High School Department. Upon receiving authorization, the researchers subsequently coordinated with the SHS Coordinator and the targeted participants to secure the necessary permits. Prior to data collection, the researchers personally informed the selected participants about the nature and purpose of the study and obtained their informed consent. Once all ethical considerations and participant rights were addressed, the researchers proceeded with the distribution of the questionnaires.

The study utilized Weighted Mean to compute and interpret data on respondents' reading interests, reading strategies, and writing proficiency. Frequency Count was employed

to organize data into categories or intervals, summarizing how often each occurred. Percentage Distribution calculated the total frequency and percentages for each category, facilitating comparisons across data. Lastly, the Pearson Correlation Coefficient (Pearson-r) was used to determine the significant relationships between reading strategies, reading interest, and writing proficiency.

Ethical Considerations

To address ethical considerations, the researchers assured the participants that all collected data would remain confidential and would not be disclosed without their explicit permission. Appropriate arrangements were made to provide each participant with a consent form.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1. Reading Strategies Used by Senior High School Students at Echague National High School

Reading Strategies	Average	Interpretation
Global Reading Strategies	2.84	Medium
Problem-Solving Strategies	3.16	Medium
Support Reading Strategies	2.86	Medium
Overall	2.90	Medium

Senior high school students at Echague National High School demonstrate a moderate level of engagement with reading strategies, as reflected in their average score of 2.90 across problem-solving strategies, support reading strategies, and global reading strategies. Problem-solving strategies, with an average score of 3.16, were the most frequently used, indicating students' ability to recognize and address reading challenges. Support reading strategies ranked second, with an average score of 2.86, suggesting a moderate but inconsistent reliance on external aids or self-support techniques. Global reading strategies, with an average score of 2.84, were the least utilized, reflecting limited engagement with higher-level processes like planning, reflecting, and critically evaluating text.

Overall, the findings suggest that while students moderately use reading strategies, their application is inconsistent, particularly with global strategies that foster in-depth comprehension. The preference for problem-solving strategies highlights their focus on immediate reading challenges, but the lack of consistent use of support and global strategies indicates potential gaps in their approach to deeper text engagement and academic success.

Table 2. Reading Interests of the Respondents

Reading Interests	Mean	Rank	Qualitative Description
1. I have the willingness and motivation to read.	3.28	5	Always
2. If I get a reading task, I do it with pleasure.	3.05	7	Often
3. I am accustomed to reading books in college and at home.	2.56	13	Often

4. I have the options between reading or other activities (such as watching TV or playing), I will choose reading.	2.83	10	Often
5. I feel the benefits of reading.	3.48	1	Always
6. I think the books/reading materials I read have influenced my behavior and attitude.	3.40	2	Always
7. When reading, I try to get the gist or the ideas in the reading materials.	3.06	6	Always
8. When I find difficulty in comprehending the materials, I repeat the reading.	3.30	3	Always
9. I read an activity every day.	2.82	11	Often
10. I make time to read articles or short stories on the wall magazine of my campus.	2.65	12	Often
11. I make special time for reading.	2.85	9	Often
12. I try to read wherever I am.	2.96	8	Often
13. I take note of important points from the materials I read to broaden my knowledge.	3.29	4	Always
14. I visit the library to access books or other reading materials.	2.41	14	Rarely
Overall	3.00		Often

The findings from the given data suggest that senior high school students generally exhibit a moderate to high level of engagement with reading, with an overall mean of 3.00, which corresponds to the often category.

Feeling the benefits of reading was ranked highest, with a mean score of 3.48, suggesting that students consistently recognize the value of reading. Moreover, reading materials influencing behavior and attitude ranked second, with a mean of 3.40, indicating that students often feel that their reading impacts their personal growth and perspectives. Meanwhile, re-reading difficult materials ranked third, with a mean of 3.30, showing that students tend to make an effort to understand the materials fully by revisiting them when faced with comprehension challenges. On the other hand, visiting the library to access books or reading materials ranked lowest with a mean score of 2.41, categorized as "rarely," indicating that students infrequently visit the library for reading materials.

Overall, while the students demonstrate a positive attitude toward reading, they are less inclined to engage in activities like visiting the library, suggesting areas for potential improvement in fostering reading habits outside the classroom.

Table 3. Level of Academic Writing Proficiency of the Senior High School Students at Echague National High School

Level	Frequency (n=192)	Percent
Beginner	11	5.73
Developing	120	62.50
Proficient	56	29.17
Advanced	5	2.60
Overall: 18.60 (Developing)		

This distribution highlights that most students are progressing but have not yet achieved full proficiency in academic writing. The qualitative interpretation of developing academic writing proficiency aligns with the categorizations outlined in the rubric used for the research survey. Based on the provided criteria, the writing lacks a clear focus, contains minimal content and explanation, has a disorganized structure, and demonstrates limited use of creative elements. Additionally, it shows poor control of grammar and mechanics. These challenges may include a lack of coherence, difficulty in conveying ideas effectively, and struggles to capture the reader's interest.

Table 4. Relationship Between Reading Interests and Writing Proficiency

Reading Interests	Writing Proficiency	
	r-value	p-value
1. I have the willingness and motivation to read.	0.05	0.45
2. If I get a reading task, I do it with pleasure.	-0.01	0.92
3. I am accustomed to reading books in college and at home.	-0.05	0.53
4. I have the options between reading or other activities (such as watching TV or playing), I will choose reading.	-0.05	0.52
5. I feel the benefits of reading.	0.03	0.73
6. I think the books/reading materials I read have influenced my behavior and attitude.	0.14	0.05*
7. When reading, I try to get the gist or the ideas in the reading materials.	0.06	0.38
8. When I find difficulty in comprehending the materials, I repeat the reading.	0.18	0.01*
9. I read an activity every day.	0.11	0.14
10. I make time to read articles or short stories on the wall magazine of my campus.	0.08	0.30
11. I make special time for reading.	0.01	0.91
12. I try to read wherever I am.	-0.10	0.16
13. I take note of important points from the materials I read to broaden my knowledge.	0.04	0.54
14. I visit the library to access books or other reading materials.	-0.10	0.19

This implies that, by reading texts that are related to what students consider as relevant to their demeanor, their writing performance will improve because they are motivated to express their ideas in writing. This shows how reading can inspire students to reflect on their thoughts and feelings, making their writing more personal and engaging. Furthermore, the result on item 8 (re-reading difficult materials for better understanding) means that it is statistically significant, this means that students who re-visit 'difficult text' may improve their

writing proficiency. This implies that there is a need to write in order to re-write better as a student. Facilitating the students to use methods like rereading of contents that the student had difficulty understanding or writing can improve performance because it assists the students hone their thinking skills.

Table 5. Relationship Between Reading Strategies and Writing Proficiency

Reading Strategies	Writing Proficiency	
	r-value	p-value
Global Reading Strategies	0.03	0.64
Problem-Solving Reading Strategies	-0.11	0.12
Support Reading Strategies	0.02	0.72
Overall Reading Strategies	0.02	0.76

The analysis of the relationship between reading strategies and writing proficiency shows that there is no significant relationship between the two. The r-values for all categories of reading strategies are low and the p-values confirm that these relationships are not statistically significant. The findings highlight this absence of considerable correlation, affirming that no substantial relationship is found between the employment of reading strategies and writing skills in the study's sample. Consequently, the results indicate that, at least in this situation, the approaches used for reading might not significantly influence writing skills.

Table 6. Relationship Between Reading Interest and Reading Strategies

Reading Interests	Global Reading		Problem-Solving		Support Reading		Overall	
	r-value	p-value	r-value	p-value	r-value	p-value	r-value	p-value
1. I have the willingness and motivation to read.	0.26	0.01*	0.02	0.74	0.29	0.01*	0.28	0.01*
2. If I get a reading task, I do it with pleasure.	0.23	0.01*	0.14	0.05*	0.16	0.03*	0.23	0.01*
3. I am accustomed to reading books in college and at home.	0.16	0.03*	0.08	0.28	0.16	0.03*	0.18	0.02*
4. I have the options between reading or other activities (such as watching TV or playing), I will choose reading.	0.01	0.86	-0.06	0.38	0.07	0.3	0.03	0.72
5. I feel the benefits of reading.	0.26	0.01*	0.1	0.16	0.2	0.01*	0.26	0.01*
6. I think the books/reading materials I read have influenced my behavior and attitude.	0.21	0.01	0.02	0.83	0.23	0.01*	0.25	0.01*
7. When reading, I try to get the gist or the ideas in the reading materials.	0.33	0.01*	0.13	0.07	0.3	0.01*	0.32	0.01*

8. When I find difficulty in comprehending the materials, I repeat the reading.	0.44	0.01*	0.09	0.19	0.4	0.01*	0.51	0.01
9. I read an activity every day.	0.18	0.01*	0.11	0.13	0.2	0.01*	0.16	0.03*
10. I make time to read articles or short stories on the wall magazine of my campus.	0.1	0.17	0.03	0.66	0.15	0.04*	0.1	0.19
11. I make special time for reading.	0.22	0.01*	0.03	0.69	0.2	0.01*	0.19	0.01*
12. I try to read wherever I am.	0.21	0.01*	0.05	0.52	0.13	0.06	0.19	0.01*
13. I take note of important points from the materials I read to broaden my knowledge.	0.34	0.01*	0.13	0.07	0.4	0.01*	0.39	0.01*
14. I visit the library to access books or other reading materials.	0.17	0.02*	0.12	0.11	0.14	0.06	0.13	0.08

The analysis of the relationship between reading interests and reading strategies shows that several reading interests are positively correlated with different categories of reading strategies. Specifically, there are significant positive correlations between students' willingness and motivation to read, enjoyment of reading tasks, and their use of global and support reading strategies.

The finding suggests that individuals who are more willing and motivated to read tend to use global reading strategies more frequently, such as skimming and predicting, which enhance comprehension. This suggests that fostering motivation and willingness to read could be an effective approach to improving the use of strategic reading methods. Furthermore, it can be interpreted that those who are willing and motivated to read are likely to employ support reading strategies more often, such as seeking help or using resources like dictionaries to aid their understanding. This implies that enhancing reading motivation can encourage the use of strategies that provide additional support, potentially improving overall reading comprehension and learning outcomes. Similarly, readers who are interested in the material use techniques such as taking notes and marking important sections.

Moreover, it can be interpreted that those who find pleasure in reading are more likely to engage in global reading strategies. This implies that individuals who enjoy reading are more likely to use global reading strategies, such as having a purpose in mind when reading, using context clues to better understand the readings, checking understanding when encountering new information, and using tables, figures, and pictures to increase comprehension. This suggests that fostering a sense of enjoyment in reading could promote the use of these effective strategies, potentially improving overall reading skills and engagement. Furthermore, the findings indicate that enjoyment of reading tasks is associated with a tendency to use support reading strategies, such as taking notes while reading, paraphrasing to understand the readings, translating English into the native language, underlining information in a text to remember it, and going back and forth in the text to find relationships among ideas in it. This suggests that fostering enjoyment in reading could

encourage the use of strategies that provide further support and aid in better understanding, potentially improving overall reading performance.

Table 7. Discourse-Based Tasks Based on the findings on Reading Strategies and Academic Writing Proficiency of the Respondents

CRITERION	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
Focus	47	24.5%
Content	20	10.4%
Organization	51	26.6%
Creative Conventions	31	16.1%
Mechanics	43	22.4%
TOTAL	192	100%

The findings indicate that a significant portion of students struggle with structuring their writing in a logical, coherent, and systematic manner. This challenge may involve issues such as poor paragraphing, unclear progression of ideas, or lack of a clear introduction, body, and conclusion, which results in confusing writing that makes it difficult for readers to follow the main points and arguments.

On the aspect of least used reading strategies, which is global reading strategies, the findings suggest that while students employ reading strategies, they are not fully utilizing the higher-level cognitive strategies required for effective reading comprehension. Global reading strategies involve a holistic approach to engaging with texts, such as setting a clear purpose for reading, previewing the text, predicting content, and critically analyzing the material. These strategies are considered essential for deep comprehension and retention, as they help readers evaluate, assess, and engage with texts in a meaningful way before, during, and after reading. However, the relatively low use of these strategies by the respondents points to the fact that students may not be fully aware of their importance or may find them more difficult to implement compared to more immediate, problem-solving strategies.

CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORKS

The reading strategies of senior high school students at Echague National High School are at a medium level, with problem-solving strategies being the most frequently utilized when engaging with academic texts. Additionally, the students demonstrated a positive interest in reading, as they often read books and articles and acknowledged the beneficial impact of such activities on their personal growth and behavior. However, while their academic writing proficiency showed promising development, with most students at a developing level and a small percentage at an advanced stage, a significant number still require targeted interventions to reach higher levels of proficiency.

The analysis of the relationship between reading interests and writing proficiency reveals that 12 of the items show no significant correlation while 2 items show a significant relationship between writing proficiency: the belief that reading materials influence behavior and attitude, and re-reading difficult materials for better understanding. Furthermore, the analysis of the relationship between reading strategies and writing proficiency shows that there is no significant relationship between the two. The r-values for all categories of reading strategies are low and the p-values confirm that these relationships are not statistically

significant. Meanwhile, the analysis of the relationship between reading interests and reading strategies shows that several reading interests are positively correlated with different categories of reading strategies. Specifically, there are significant positive correlations between students' willingness and motivation to read, enjoyment of reading tasks, and their use of global and support reading strategies.

Lastly, the study's findings suggest that students face significant challenges in organizing their academic writing, particularly in organization, focus, and mechanics. Specifically, organization was identified as the most difficult criterion, with a considerable portion of students struggling to structure their essays coherently. This difficulty reflects problems in creating logical flow, clear paragraphing, and the proper introduction-body-conclusion structure. Meanwhile, the findings also showed that global reading strategies (GLOB) were significantly lower than other strategies, this indicates that they may not fully understand or engage in high-level cognitive reading strategies such as setting a purpose, previewing the text, or critically analyzing the content.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that there are no conflicts of interest regarding the publication of this paper.

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